

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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GREEN TECHNOLOGIES INVESTMENT AND THE PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article discusses the attraction of foreign investments for the development of green technologies in our country, the analysis of their effective use, and the prospects of the green economy. It analyzes the factors influencing environmental protection, combating climate change, and the effective use of renewable energy sources. Within the scope of attracting foreign investments and their effective utilization, existing shortcomings have been identified, and the tasks to address them have been outlined. Scientific proposals and practical recommendations for improving the system of attracting foreign investments to the national economy have been developed.

Key words: Green economy, green technologies, sustainable development, climate change, renewable energy, environmental sustainability, environmental protection, green investments, sustainable energy, green bonds.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimizga yashil texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish, ulardan samarali foydalanish tahlili va yashil iqtisodiyotning istiqbollari muhokama qilingan. Yashil texnologiyalar atrof-muhitni himoya qilish, iqlim o'zgarishlariga qarshi kurashish va qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalaridan samarali foydalanish jarayonlariga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillarni tahlil etib berilgan. Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari doirasida mavjud kamchiliklar aniqlangan hamds ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari bo'yicha amalga oshirish lozim bo'lgan vazifalar yoritilgan. Milliy iqtisodiyotga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish tizimini takomillashtirishga doir ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar shakllantirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil texnologiyalar, barqaror rivojlanish, iqlim o'zgarishi, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya, ekologik barqarorlik, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, yashil investitsiyalar, barqaror energiya, yashil obligatsiyalar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается привлечение иностранных инвестиций для развития зелёных технологий в нашей стране, анализ их эффективного использования и перспективы зелёной экономики. Приведён анализ факторов, влияющих на защиту окружающей среды, борьбу с изменением климата и эффективное использование возобновляемых источников энергии. Выявлены существующие недостатки в привлечении иностранных инвестиций и их эффективном использовании, а также представлены задачи, которые необходимо решить для устранения этих проблем. Разработаны научные предложения и практические рекомендации по совершенствованию системы привлечения иностранных инвестиций в национальную экономику.

Ключевые слова: Зелёная экономика, зелёные технологии, устойчивое развитие, изменение климата, возобновляемая энергия, экологическая устойчивость, защита окружающей среды, зелёные инвестиции, устойчивая энергия, зелёные облигации.

INTRODUCTION

The continuation of negative environmental trends could lead to even more dangerous consequences, both for humanity as a whole and for individual countries. In particular, air pollution has reached a critical level in the urban areas of Uzbekistan. Industrial waste, outdated infrastructure, and old transportation vehicles are causing the deterioration of air quality. This poses a significant threat to public health, as respiratory diseases and other related health issues are increasing. Currently, this global issue is being addressed through innovative solutions aimed at environmental protection, combating climate change, and effectively using renewable energy sources, which are considered green technologies. These solutions are crucial for improving energy efficiency, reducing waste, and ensuring environmental safety. The green economy is an economic model that harmonizes

economic development and environmental sustainability by promoting the rational use of resources, ensuring social stability, and addressing environmental issues. Investments in green technologies lead to the creation of new opportunities in the global economy, development of new jobs, and technological innovations. At the same time, such investments enable effective environmental protection and the fight against climate change. The prospects of the green economy are vast, as this sector not only ensures environmental sustainability but also supports economic and social development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Uzbekistan has joined the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Climate Agreement. Additionally, in 2019, Uzbekistan adopted the “Green Economy Transition Strategy.” This strategy aims to significantly reduce carbon consumption in the country, introduce environmentally clean and resource-efficient technologies across all sectors of the economy, and widely use renewable and efficient energy sources. Furthermore, in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Resolution No. 436), titled “Measures to Improve the Effectiveness of reforms aimed at transitioning Uzbekistan to a ‘Green’ Economy by 2030,” the tasks set out in the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 are to be implemented. The decree outlines measures to improve the effectiveness of actions being taken under Uzbekistan’s “Green Economy Transition Strategy,” which include ensuring “green” and inclusive economic growth, expanding the use of renewable energy sources, and further increasing resource efficiency across all sectors of the economy. A program and action plan were set to ensure the transition to a “green” economy and “green” growth in Uzbekistan by 2030. [1]

It is known to us that the most important factor in the economic development of countries is economic growth. Like a coin with two sides, economic growth has both positive and negative aspects. One of the global problems of the 21st century, in particular, is the increasing environmental risks caused by pollution. Environmental degradation (climate change, desertification, loss of biodiversity), limited and depleting natural capital, the growing scale of poverty, shortages of freshwater, food, and energy, and inequality between people and countries are all signs of the imperfection of the current economic system. Due to the reasons mentioned above, the existing economic model is referred to as the “brown economy.” [6]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research work used comparative and statistical methods, systematic analysis and synthesis. The information base for the study was official statistical data and foreign sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A green economy is an economic system aimed at ensuring environmental sustainability, promoting social justice, and enhancing economic stability. Green technologies are the foundation of this system, and they are widely used in utilizing renewable energy sources, reducing waste, and protecting the environment. Today, investments in green technologies and the prospects of the green economy are being widely discussed on a global scale. However, there are also challenges, problems that need to be addressed, and significant opportunities in these sectors. Today, the “green economy” is considered the main driver of sustainable development for countries around the world, and it is recognized that the driving force behind it is the “green” technologies and the investments being made in them. Green technologies are an innovative set of technologies that are receiving serious attention.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in the book “*The Strategy of New Uzbekistan*” emphasized the importance of implementing the “Green Economy” transition strategy. He stated that it is essential to reduce the energy and resource capacity of the economy, widely introduce resource-efficient technologies in production, expand the use of renewable technologies, and develop nuclear energy. [4]

Green technologies aim to save energy and resources, reduce carbon emissions, utilize alternative energy sources, cultivate organic agricultural products, recycle waste, and generally develop the economy without harming nature and the environment, while ensuring the ecological safety of humanity. [5]

Green technology refers to innovative solutions focused on environmental protection, ensuring ecological sustainability, and the efficient use of energy sources and resources. These technologies help reduce environmental damage in all aspects.

The importance of applying green technologies is crucial in combating climate change, reducing energy and resource consumption, preventing the depletion of natural resources, increasing the environmental efficiency of the global economy, introducing innovation and new technologies, and creating new jobs (Table 1).

Table 1. Composition of green technologies.

1	Renewable energy sources:	
1.1	Solar energy	Generating electricity from the sun using solar batteries and photovoltaic panels. Solar energy provides a new energy source without harming the environment.
1.2	Wind energy	Converting the kinetic energy of wind into electrical energy using wind turbines. Wind energy is a renewable and environmentally friendly source.
1.3	Hydroelectric energy	Generating electricity from water currents or the movement of water. This technology also ensures the efficient use of natural resources.
1.4	Geothermal energy	Generating electricity and heat energy by utilizing geothermal heat. This technology is sustainable and does not harm the environment.
2	Energy efficiency and energy conservation:	
2.1	Energy-efficient building materials	Green technologies develop new building materials, such as insulation materials for heat retention, energy-efficient windows, walls, and other insulating materials.
2.2	LED lights	LED lights consume less energy and last longer compared to traditional bulbs.
2.3	Energy recovery systems	Improving energy efficiency in buildings through energy recovery systems (such as installing heat pumps and solar collectors).
2.4	Smart systems	Smart homes and smart city systems, which help manage electricity, water, and other resources efficiently.
3	Recycling and waste management.	
3.1	Waste recycling	Producing new products by recycling plastic, metal, paper, and other materials. This process helps reduce waste and create new resources.
3.2	Composting	Turning organic waste (food scraps, garden materials) into compost. This technology helps improve soil quality and reduce waste.
3.3	Energy generation from waste	Generating energy from biomass and other organic materials (such as biogas systems) creates an environmentally friendly energy source.
4	Green transportation:	
4.1	Electric vehicles	Electric cars, buses, and bicycles do not harm the environment and help prevent the emission of harmful gases
4.2	Hybrid cars	«Vehicles powered by electric and gasoline engines. This technology helps reduce carbon emissions
4.3	Environmental public transportation systems	Environmentally friendly buses, metros, trams, and other public transport systems reduce harmful emissions to the environment.
4.4	Bicycle and pedestrian lanes	Bicycle and pedestrian lanes are built to develop eco-friendly transportation in urban infrastructure.
5	Organic agriculture and smart farming	
5.1	Organic farming	Growing agricultural products using eco-friendly methods without the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides.
5.2	Smart farming	Ensuring efficient irrigation, crop optimization, and resource management using modern technologies.
5.3	Water resource management	Saving and using water efficiently with the help of smart systems. For example, managing water effectively in crop irrigation.
6	Green building (eco-friendly buildings):	
6.1	Green buildings	Eco-friendly buildings that incorporate energy-efficient construction materials, solar panels, heat pumps, and other green technologies
6.2	Passive houses	Energy-efficient and highly insulated homes that retain heat well against changes in the external environment.

6.3	Using solar and wind energy	Generating energy by installing solar panels and wind turbines in buildings.
7	Water conservation technologies:	
7.1	Water recycling and reuse systems	Water purification and reuse systems can be installed in homes, offices, and industrial enterprises. These systems help in efficient water usage and conservation.
7.2	Water-efficient agriculture	Reducing water consumption in farming through water-saving technologies.
7.3	Water conservation systems	Smart systems and technologies are installed in buildings and gardens to save water.

Investments in renewable energy sources: In 2023, investments in renewable energy reached \$450 billion. Over the past years, investments, particularly in the solar and wind energy sectors, have significantly increased. For example, in 2020, investments in solar energy amounted to \$130 billion, and by 2023, this figure rose to \$180 billion. Meanwhile, investments in the electric vehicle market are also growing rapidly, reaching \$160 billion by 2023.

Moreover, environmental pollution can also be reduced through smart transportation systems. For instance, demand for electric vehicles is increasing in Europe. By 2023, the electric vehicle market size reached \$160 billion, and it is expected to grow to \$300 billion by 2025. **Manufacturers in the electric vehicle and solar energy sectors** are creating new job opportunities. In 2022, **the electric vehicle** manufacturing sector created over 1.5 million new jobs. By 2023, this number reached 3 million (Table 2).

Table 2. Investment amount for green technologies in 2024.

Directions	Amount of investment	Sources
Renewable energy sources	\$450 - \$600 million	Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan- https://minenergy.uz/uz
Utilizing solar energy	\$120 - \$150 million	Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan- https://minenergy.uz/uz
Utilizing wind energy	\$50 - \$80 million	Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan- https://minenergy.uz/uz
Expanding energy efficiency	\$60 - \$90 million	Uzbekistan's 'Green Economy
Electric vehicles in transportation	\$20 - \$50 million	Electric transport projects, eco-friendly construction programs
Green building	\$30 - \$70 million	Green building projects, environmental standards
Water recycling and water resource conservation	\$10 - \$30 million	Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan — eco.gov.uz .

In 2023, global investments in the green technology market reached 500 billion dollars. This figure was only 350 billion dollars in 2020, meaning that the annual growth rate of investments in the green technology sector was 10-12%. These numbers indicate that the sector is developing globally and becoming an important economic sector.

The current digital transformation is closely related to green technologies. These include digital technologies such as "Smart Cities," **IoT (Internet of Things)**, and blockchain, which help ensure the effective functioning of the green economy. For example, through the implementation of smart systems in New York City, energy consumption was reduced by 15%. At the same time, countries like India and China are developing new innovations as a result of applying digital technologies.

IoT (Internet of Things) is a network of specialized devices known as Internet-enabled devices, used for collecting and exchanging real-time data over the internet or other networks. Internet-enabled devices (**IoT**) refer to physical objects that are connected to the internet and can transmit data online, such as vehicles, household appliances, wearable devices, and others. [7.]

With the help of IoT technologies, significant changes have been made in the management of water resources in agriculture and energy conservation. In 2023, investments in IoT technologies reached 50 billion dollars, and by 2025, the investment volume in this market is expected to reach 1 trillion dollars.

The future prospects of the green economy are extremely large. The role of green technologies in implementing this process is increasing. By 2030, the green technology and solar energy sectors are expected to account for more than 30% of the global economy. This growth will be achieved primarily through reducing the carbon footprint, investments in renewable energy sources, and the development of green infrastructure.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Green technologies and the green economy are expected to become an integral part of the global economy today. Climate change, environmental protection, and ensuring sustainable development are urgent issues on a global scale, with increasing responsibility for each country and company in this regard. Investments in areas such as renewable energy sources, improving energy efficiency, and creating environmental infrastructure are growing every year. These changes are not only helping to ensure ecological sustainability but also playing a crucial role in creating new jobs, stimulating economic growth, and promoting social justice. At the same time, there are still many challenges in the process of expanding investments and technologies aimed at the green economy. To develop green technologies, it is necessary to enhance the required infrastructure, political support, and global cooperation. The success of this process depends on the cooperation between states, the private sector, and public organizations. The success of this system largely depends on the cooperation between countries, proper financial incentives, effective technological development, and public awareness. Through green technologies and investments, we must strengthen financial incentives to create new opportunities to address the climate crisis, solve environmental issues, and ensure sustainable development. In order to attract investments into the green economy, both governments and the private sector need to provide more financial incentives. Expanding financial mechanisms based on ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) indicators and promoting green bonds are of particular importance for expanding green technologies, especially in developing countries. The prospects for the green economy are immense, and how actively each country engages in this process will be of vital importance for its future.

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

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Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

